

Human Values in Hinduism

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Abstract

Human values are the core of what makes us human, it is intrinsic to our identity. Individuals can follow human values as guides to guide their day-to-day activities. Among the fundamental inherent values of humans are truth, honesty, loyalty, love, peace, etc. Hinduism, the world's oldest and most prominent religion, practiced these human values for a very long time and stands still practiced today. Hindus generally follow *yamas* i.e., moral values to be followed while performing any action, and *niyamas* i.e., the practices followed in daily routine. These practices help them feel comfortable with moral values and develop into a better person. Hindus get instructions for their practices from their texts. Hindu texts are mainly *Vedas*, *Upaniṣad*, *Epics* and *Purānas*. The fundamental principle of Hinduism is to inculcate and practice certain fundamental human values. These values relate to how individuals live their daily lives. It is said in Hinduism, Truth alone wins, not falsehoods *satyameva jayate nānṛtaṃ, ahiṃsā Paramo Dharma*, it is the highest moral virtue. *Amritasya Putrāḥ Vayam* - We are all created of the immortal. Other human values in Hinduism are Honesty, Compassion, Forgiveness, Sweet speech, Dana, Self-Control, Contentment, Acceptance, Acceptance, Listening to self-conscience and Enlightenment.

Key words: Truthfulness, Non-Violence, Honesty, Compassion, Forgiveness, Contentment, Tithing, Acceptance

Introduction:

Human values can be defined as those values that are intrinsic to our identity and are at the core of what makes us human. Individuals can follow human values as guides to guide their day-to-day activities and change their behaviour as a guidebook for their way of life. Among the fundamental inherent values of humans are truth, honesty, loyalty, love, peace, etc. These human values are crucial for maintaining peace and protecting society. In Hinduism, these human values have been practiced for a very long time, and are still practiced today.

Hinduism and Hindu Scriptures:

Hinduism is the world's oldest and most prominent religion, also called *Sanātana Dharma*. There is no static and single belief In Hinduism, it includes a variety of beliefs and practices. Hindus generally follow '*Yamas*' and '*Niyamas*'. '*Yamas*' are moral values to be followed while performing any action. '*Niyamas*' are the practices followed in daily routine. Hindus follow certain practices like chanting (*Japa*), Purity (*Śauca*), Austerity (*Tapas*), Sacred vows (*Vrata*), Remorse, donations, worshipping, modesty, etc. All these practices help them feel comfortable with moral values and develop into a better person. The teachings of Hinduism are based on general principles of *dharma* and *karma* as well as desire (*kāma*) to differentiate truth from illusion i.e., to achieve '*Mokṣa*'. '*Dharma*', '*Artha*', '*Karma*' and '*Mokṣa*' are *Puruṣārthas* of Hinduism.

There are numerous scriptures in Hinduism, which are classified as '*Śruti*' and '*Smṛti*'. '*Śruti*' primarily refers to the Vedas. Hindu Vedas are divided into four categories - *Rig Veda*, *Sāma Veda*, *Yajur Veda*, and *Atharva Veda*. Each Veda is sub divided into four texts - *Samhitā*, *Brāhmana*, *Āranyaka* and *Upaniṣad*. The four Vedas contain descriptions of '*Karmakānda*' and '*Jñānakānda*'. '*Karmakānda*'

encompasses Hindu rituals and prayers. 'Jñānakānda' encompasses ontological realities such as self-consciousness, God and Brahman. *Smṛti* includes the Hindu epics *Mahābhārata* and *Rāmāyana* along with the *Purānas*. The *Bhagavadgītā* is also an integral part of the *Mahābhārata*. The *Purānas* contain the mythologies of Hinduism. The set-of teachings included in *Jñānakānda* is known as *Vedānta*. *Vedānta* is not limited to one book as a source of *Vedānta* philosophy, *Upaniṣad*, *Bhagavadgītā* and *Brahma Sūtras* are the constituents of *Vedānta* philosophy. Moreover, there are other scriptures for children, such as the *Panchatantra*. 'Panchatantra' contains wonderful ancient Indian social stories that teach moral lessons to children.

Human Values in Hinduism:

A fundamental principle of Hinduism is to inculcate and practice certain fundamental human values. These values relate to how individuals live their daily lives. The basic human values in Hinduism are described as follows:

1. Truthfulness (*Satyam*):

Satya (truth) is a much-discussed concept in *Vedas* and *Upaniṣads*. *Satya* is considered in *Vedas* as *ṛta* and without it, the universe and reality cannot function. In the *Bṛhadāranyaka Upaniṣad* *Satya* is referred as Brahman (being, true self). *Satya* (truth) is equated with *dharma* i.e., law of morality, ethics, righteousness, in *Bṛhadāranyaka Upaniṣad*, hymn I.4.xiv *Taittiriya Upaniṣad*'s hymn 11.11 states, "Speak the *Satya* (truth), conduct yourself according to the *Dharma* (morality, ethics, law)". The *Mundaka Upaniṣad* states "*satyameva jayate nānṛtam*". Truth alone wins, not falsehood. (3.1.6) *Sandilya Upaniṣad* defines *Satya* as "the speaking of the truth that conduces to the well-being of creatures, through the actions of one's mind, speech or body." The Epic *Mahābhārata* repeatedly emphasizes that *Satya* is a basic virtue because everything and everyone depends on and relies on *Satya*. The *Śānti Parva* of the *Mahābhārata* states "*satyasya vacanam sādhu na satyād vidyate param | satyena vidhṛtam sarvaṃ sarvaṃ satye pratiṣṭhitam*." Speaking truth always admirable. Nothing is higher than truth. Everything is upheld by truth and rests upon truth.

Truth always prevails. It is possible that the lie may seem to win in the short term but the truth will win in the long run. But if the truth hurts, it is better to be silent than to speak. So the beautiful truth should be spoken, '*Satyam Brooyat, Priam Brooyat*'. For example, if a person is ill and his life is at risk, telling the truth about the illness and the risk to the patient's life may harm the patient. So in that case it is better to keep quiet.

2. Non-Violence (*Ahiṃsā*):

Ahiṃsā literary means 'nonviolence', it is an ancient Indian principle that applies to all living beings. It is a key virtue in Hinduism. *Ahiṃsā* as an ethical concept evolved in the *Vedic* texts. *Chāndogya Upaniṣad*, use the term *Ahiṃsā* in the sense familiar in Hinduism as a code of conduct. The epic *Mahābhārata* has multiple mentions of the phrase *Ahiṃsā Paramo Dharma*, which literally means: non-violence is the highest moral virtue. Our *Dharma* is not to harm others for our personal benefits. Hinduism declares non-violence as one of the primary virtues, and any killing or harming is against moral life (*dharma*). *Upaniṣads* and Hindu Epics suggest that one should prefer to be vegetarian and should refrain from overeating and consuming meat.

3. Non-Stealing (*Asteya*):

Asteya actually means "not to steal", "not to cheat" or not to manipulate others' property for one's own gain. As a virtue, *Asteya* asserts that not only is one not to "steal" through one's actions, one does not want to encourage deception in speech or writing, or even to deceive one's thoughts. *Asteya* is a widely discussed virtue in the ethical theories of Hinduism. It is defined in Hindu scripts as "the abstinence, in one's deeds or words or thoughts, from unauthorized appropriation of things of value from another human being". In the *Yoga Sūtras*, *Asteya* (non-stealing) is listed as the third *yamas* or virtue of self-restraint, "*ahiṃsā-satya-asteya-brahmacarya-aparigrahaḥ yamāḥ*". (2.30)

4. Honesty (*Ārjavam*):

Ārjavam literally means sincerity, straightness and non-hypocrisy. Everyone should be simple, straightforward, open as well as honest and should not follow hypocrisy. There should be

integration between body, mind and soul. *Ārjavā* is one of the ten virtuous restraints (*yamas*) taught in ancient Indian texts such as *Śāṅḍilya Upaniṣad*, and also in *Svātmārāma*. In some texts, such as by Ādi Śāṅkara, this virtue is called *bhavasamsuddhi*. It is explained as purity of motive and freedom of the mind from hypocrisy. It is considered as a virtue that gives one the ability to act and live without anxiety, anger, prejudice, inner conflict or confusion. *Bhagavadgītā* also discussed about it in verse 17.16, “*Manah-prasādaḥ saumyatvaṁ maunam ātma-vinigrahaḥ | Bhāva-saṁśuddhir ity etat tapo mānasam uchyate.*” The *Mahābhārata* describes *Ārjavam* (non-hypocrisy) as a virtue along with *Akrodha* (non-anger), *Kṣamā* (forgiveness) and others. (Book 12 Chapter 60) The Epic also explains how and why hypocrisy arises, suggesting that it is a derivative of the sin of covetousness, greed and attachment to superficial possessions. (Book 12 Chapter 278)

5. Compassion (*Dayā*):

Compassion (*Dayā*) is explained in classical literature of Hinduism as virtue. The virtue of compassion for all living beings is a central concept in Hindu philosophy. The *Padma Purāna* defines *Dayā* as the desire to alleviate others' sorrows and difficulties by exerting whatever effort it takes. According to the *Matsya Purāna*, *Dayā* is the value that treats all living beings (including humans) as one's own self, wanting their welfare and good. *Matsya Purāna* claims, that such compassion is one of the necessary paths to happiness. Compassion in Hindu philosophy is also called *Karunā*, which means putting one's mind in the other person's favour, by which one seeks to help alleviate their suffering through an act of *Karunā* (compassion). *Anukampa*, another word for compassion, refers to one's state when one has seen and understood the pain and suffering of another. Compassion is the state in which one sees all living beings as part of oneself and then sees everyone's suffering as one's own suffering. Compassion towards all living beings, including those who are strangers and those who are enemies, is seen as a noble virtue.

6. Forgiveness (*Kṣamā*):

Vedic literature and epics of Hinduism teach us *Kṣamā* (Forgiveness). According to Hinduism, a person who does not forgive carries with them the baggage of past wrongs, negative feelings, anger, and unresolved emotions that affect their present and future. In Hinduism, it is not only necessary to forgive others, but also to seek forgiveness if we have wronged them. Forgiveness will ultimately lead to peace. It forms the basis of non-violence. The epic *Mahābhārata* in Book 3, *Vana Parva*, Section XXIX says, “Forgiveness is virtue; forgiveness is sacrifice; forgiveness is the *Vedas*; forgiveness is the *Śruti*. Forgiveness protecteth the ascetic merit of the future; forgiveness is asceticism; forgiveness is holiness; and by forgiveness is it that the universe is held together.”

7. Sweet speech (*Mādhuryam*):

Hinduism teaches us the importance of having a sweet personality and speaking sweetly. Rudeness, harshness, and impoliteness should be avoided. It is essential for the individual to be pious and to use sweet words at all times. One must be firm but at the same time, one must be pure, cheerful, pleasant and kind-hearted. *Bhakti-rasamṛta-sindhu* says *Mādhuryam* as “*mādhuryam – tan mādhuryam bhaved yatra ceṣṭādeḥ sprhaṇīyatā*” (2.1.257).

8. Tithing (*Dāna*):

It is believed in Hinduism that the more you give more you get. *Dāna* means giving, often in the context of donation and charity. In other contexts, such as rituals, it can simply refer to the act of giving something. *Dāna* is related to and mentioned in ancient texts with concepts of *Paropakāra* which means benevolent deed, helping others; *Dakṣiṇa* which means gift or fee one can afford; and *Bhikṣā*, which means alms. Charity (*Dāna*) is held as a noble deed in Hinduism, to be done without expectation of any return from those who receive the charity. It helps in purity by teaching us the lessons of distributing and sharing with others.

The *Rigveda* has the earliest discussion of *dāna* in the *Vedas*. *Bṛihadaranyaka Upaniṣad*, states that three characteristics of a good, developed person are self-restraint (*damah*), compassion or love for all sentient life (*dayā*), and charity (*dāna*). “*Tadetat trayam śikshet damam, dānam, dayām iti*” (V.ii.3). Similarly, in Book III, *Chāndogya Upaniṣad* states that a virtuous life requires: *tapas* (asceticism), *dāna* (charity), *ārjava* (straightforwardness), *ahimsā* (non-injury to all sentient beings) and *satyavacana* (truthfulness). *Bhagavadgītā* in verses 17.20 to 17.22 describes the right and wrong

forms of *dāna*. *Bhagavadgītā* suggests steadiness in *sātत्विकamdāna* as one given without expectation of return, at the proper time and place, and to a worthy person is better. *Tamasdāna* as one given with contempt, to unworthy person(s), at a wrong place and time should be avoided. The *Ādi Parva* of the Hindu Epic *Mahābhārata*, in Chapter 91, states that a person should first acquire wealth by honest means, then start charity; be hospitable to those who come to Him; never inflict pain on any living creature, and he shares a portion of what he eats with others.

9. Free from Sin (Akalkata):

Hinduism teaches us not to commit any sinful act. According to the law of *karma*, everyone is rewarded according to his actions, sooner or later, in absolute and exact measure. Every action whether good or bad, positive or negative, virtuous or vicious, exalted or sinful is rewarded. If one commits a sin or bad deed, evil will return to him. Therefore, one should always do good *karma* so that good will returns to one. Therefore, he should always try his best to stay away from sin or bad action.

10. Self-Control (Damah):

Hinduism teaches us control over our emotions and senses. A self-controlled person will be guided by wisdom and kindness rather than desire. Self-control not only promotes humility but elevates man to the level of God. But lack of self-control can lead a person down the wrong path. A self-controlled person has neither impression of praise nor fear of criticism. He does everything according to moral and ethical values.

As mentioned earlier *Brihadaranyaka Upaniṣad* states that three characteristics of a good, developed person are self-restraint (*damah*), compassion and love for all sentient life (*dayā*), and charity (*dāna*). In Hinduism literature dedicated to yoga, self-Control is expounded with the concept of *yamas*. According to *Saṭsampad*, self-Control (*damah*) is one of the six cardinal virtues.

11. Contentment (Santośa):

Contentment is a state of complete satisfaction or the lack of *trṣṇa* (craving). Hinduism believes in the liberation of the soul which is possible only if a person is contented. When a person attains contentment, he will feel peace of mind, ease in life and free from all worries and tensions. A contented person will experience introversion as well as steadiness and will attain the highest transcendental meditation.

Santośais broadly discussed as an important virtue and ethical concept in many ancient and medieval texts of Hinduism like *Purānas*, *Upaniṣad*, and *Yoga Śāstra*. *Mahābhārata* discussed that there is no higher experience than contentment (*Santośa*). It is the highest heaven, the highest bliss.

12. Acceptance:

Everyone should do selfless actions according to his *Dharma* and without thinking of consequences. Whatever the consequence of any action should be accepted as '*Prasāda*'- the gift of God. Whether the result of an action is desirable or undesirable, then one should not get emotionally disturbed or stronger. A person should accept the results without worrying about them. It is important to concentrate only on actions, not on results.

Bhagavadgītā Verse 47 in the Chapter 2 says "*karmany-evādhikāras te mā phaleṣu kadāchana | mā karma-phala-hetur bhūr mā te saṅgo 'stvakarmani'*". One should act as a duty without being attached to the results of action. Any work performed without desired results will develop individuals into better personalities.

13. Each and every one is one:

In Hinduism, it is believed that everyone is alike. The basic nature of a human being is not limited to the body or the mind. There is a spirit, or spark of God, within each soul that lies beyond both of these. *Svetasvatara Upaniṣad* says '*Amritasya Putrah Vayam*' - "We are all begotten of the immortal." '*Ātma*'- Soul is a part of God and exists in everyone. *Bhagavadgītā* says "*sarva-bhūta-stham ātmānam sarva-bhūtāni chātmani*". (Verse 29, Chapter 6)

One should follow one's inner consciousness and see all others within oneself. One should listen to others' problems and try to solve them because these problems are one's own. When a person feels everyone alike, he will be transcended into an elevated soul.

14. Listen to self-conscience:

An individual should listen to his own conscience whenever he is unsure whether what he is doing is correct or wrong. In that case, the almighty will guide him to the right path and he will be released from all the sins for that action. Gandhiji has said in respect of the determination of truth and falsity, that everyone should abide by the direction of his self- conscience. According to him the direction of self-conscience, of God, or of the heart is one. so, it is infallible. *Bhagavadgītā*, chapter-18, verse-66 says “*sarva-dharmān parityajya mām ekam śharaṇam vraja | aham tvām sarva-pāpēbhyo mokṣhayiṣhyāmi mā śhuchah*”. When Arjuna was in dilemma that whether it is appropriate to kill his own cousins, then Lord Krishna enlightens him to choose and perform the moral and righteous action. Thus, Arjuna fought in the *Mahābhārata* war and establish the victory of the righteous over the unrighteous.

15. Enlightenment:

In Hindu traditions, Enlightenment or *Mokṣa* is a central concept. It is the utmost aim of human life. According to Hinduism, one can evolve through continuous upgradation of knowledge. A person’s knowledge is limited by his capabilities, likes and dislikes, environment and upbringing background. But one should always try to upgrade knowledge and reach the ultimate level. Then one can realize his ‘self’ and become fully enlightened. Enlightenment or *Mokṣa* is the param *Puruṣārth* in Hinduism.

Conclusion:

So, it can be said that every person should act and should choose righteous tasks. The actions of an individual determine his personality. One should always try to refrain from deception, be free from all bad events and achieve the ultimate goal of becoming a superior personality. This can be achieved through the moral and ethical teachings of Hinduism. Those whose lives reflect these moral and ethical ideals are regarded as great people. Goodness and welfare are achieved by great people, and these great people epitomize human values. They are the ones who can play a leading role in practicing human values and applying them in thought and action to countless people in the individual society as well as the global society.

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